

ON THE VELOCITY OF HYDRATION AND DEHYDRATION OF NICKEL SULPHATE.

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A method has been developed by which it is possible to fix up the composition of the hydrates of inorganic salts by studying the velocity of their thermal dehydration under a fixed experimental condition. The process of hydration seems to be more complex and do not yield the above information.

The purpose of this note is to describe the technique of a method used for the measurement of the velocity of dehydration and hydration of some inorganic salts and also to present some results obtained, by which it has been found possible to fix up the composition of the hydrates of these salts. It has also been found that the rates of dehydration can be accelerated or retarded, and in some cases the temperature of decomposition of the hydrates lowered by the catalytic action of some finely divided metallic powders and salts. But the general feature of dehydration curve shows a number of breaks, with or without the presence of catalysts, whose position as regards composition of the hydrates remain unaltered by variations of the superincumbent pressure or by a variation of the temperature of dehydration, provided the latter be sufficiently high to decompose the hydrates whose composition is to be revealed. The present paper is however concerned with measurements on unadulterated and pure hydrated nickel sulphate, and though data have been obtained at 150°, 220° and 300° only, the figures for the last temperature are presented, as here all the features of dehydration are fully developed.

It is well known that anhydrous nickel sulphate can be prepared by heating the hydrated salt to dull redness (*vide* Mellor, "Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. XV, p. 453). The anhydrous salt when crystallised from an aqueous solution at a low temperature contains seven molecules of water of hydration. When the usual physicochemical methods are adopted for determining the composition of the hydrates, it is found that stable molecules of the salt may exist in aqueous solution holding 1 to 7 molecules of water of hydration. It is also found that as the temperature of the salt is raised, more and more molecules of water of hydration are shaken off progressively up to a total number of six. The last molecule of water of hydration, which seems to be very tenacious, takes a longer time to go out, and persists up to 280°. After this it escapes on further heating.

Rakuzin and Brodsky (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1927, **40**, 836) have studied the thermal dehydration of this salt. They find that it takes 5.5 hours of heating for obtaining a loss of weight corresponding to the escape of 4.5 molecules of water of hydration. The loss of weight with time has not, however, been studied by these authors in a quantitative way and so the formation of the hydrates can not be fixed from their measurements. An analogous paper on the hydration of anhydrous copper sulphate by Davis and Eyre (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **A104**, 512) shows that the absorption of moisture takes place in a series of discontinuous steps. Their curves representing the quantity of moisture gained as a function of time show that in the case of copper sulphate the segments of the curve are either straight lines or parabolas. But the points corresponding to the breaks do not show the existence of stable hydrates.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Of the various forms of apparatus used for analysing the above problem the one described below was found most useful and convenient. The container holding the salt was always in the form of a pyrex or metallic test-tube, the top of which was either closed or sealed. It was provided with a side-tube which was joined to a stop-cock. The latter in turn was connected with a U-tube containing P_2O_5 . The second arm of this U-tube was joined to a manometer and a pump by a flexible rubber tubing. The test-tube with its contents was put in a furnace at the desired temperature, and the pressure of the air over the salt was generally maintained at 2 cm. of Hg. Weights were taken every 10 minutes in the beginning and at longer intervals later on. In order to enable the test-tube and the salt to take up the experimental temperature quickly, after each weight has been taken, the former was temporarily put in a furnace at 600° , when generally within one minute the experimental temperature was obtained. Immediately after this the test-tube was transferred to the dehydrating furnace. Similarly to arrest the process of dehydration, when it was necessary to take weights at the end of a desired time, the test-tube was suddenly plunged in cold water to freeze the process. The equivalent correction to the time factor due to this pre-heating and post-cooling period was fixed up from a preliminary blank experiment. This inertial period was of course much less with the metallic vessel as compared with the glass one. It was also found convenient to mix about an equal weight of finely powdered glass with the salt which was also in the powdered form. This made the process of

dehydration more uniform as the crystals were kept separated from each other by the intervening glass fragments. The data for the initial portion of the curve was also obtained separately by taking several successive samples of the salt and determining their losses in weight after periods of heating lasting 10, 20 and 30 minutes., etc. Here the disturbing effects, which creep in the measurements of time when the weights are taken in several successive stages, vanish excepting for a common corrective addition to the heating time, which is necessary to bring the substance to the experimental temperature at the beginning of the experiment. Attempts were also made to take the weight of the samples with the help of a spring balance mounted in vacuum, but it was not found convenient. For the study of the rate of hydration, the cover of a test-tube holding the salt was removed and it was kept in a desiccator case (temp. = 32°) containing enough water to saturate the inside. Readings were taken at regular intervals as in the case of dehydration.

R E S U L T S.

The data obtained are shown on a simplified scheme by plotting ' N ', the number of molecules of water of hydration lost (in the case of dehydration), or gained (in the case of hydration) per molecule of NiSO_4 , as a function of the time, as in Fig. 1 (dehydration) or Fig. 2 (hydration). These points are marked in circles. In Fig. 1 $dN/dt \rightarrow N$ curve has been drawn marked with crosses and also $\log dN/dt \rightarrow N$, marked with stars. In the curves dN/dt has been represented as ' V ', the velocity of dehydration, expressed as the number of molecules of H_2O lost per molecule of NiSO_4 .

Two typical sets of observations are given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I.

M. W. of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} = 280.86$. $N =$ Number of mol. of H_2O per mol. of NiSO_4 .

Time of heating.	Wt. of salt	Wt. lost.	N .	Time of heating.	Wt. of salt.	Wt. lost.	N .
0 min.	15.571 g.			80 min.	10.543 g.	5.028 g.	5.031
10	14.461	1.110 g.	1.111	100	10.153	5.418	5.421
20	13.538	2.033	2.034	120	9.829	5.742	5.745
30	12.850	2.721	2.723	150	9.562	6.009	6.012
40	12.242	3.329	3.331	180	9.290	6.281	6.284
50	11.821	3.750	3.752	210	9.072	6.499	6.503
60	11.360	4.211	4.213	240	8.904	6.667	6.671

TABLE II.

Duration of heating.	Wt. of salt Original.	Wt. of salt Final.	Loss of wt.	N .	Duration of heating.	Wt. of salt Original.	Wt. of salt Final.	Loss of wt.	N .
0.7 min.	7.215 g.	6.913 g.	0.302 g.	0.652	0.35 min.	7.082	5.664	1.551	3.412
0.15	7.045	6.535	0.680	1.505	0.45	7.223	5.354	1.861	4.014
0.25	7.471	6.016	1.199	2.500	0.55	7.148	5.148	2.067	4.504

DISCUSSION.

In the process of dehydration of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, three molecules of water of crystallisation escape within 40 minutes. Then the dehydration process slows down and the curve changes its nature at this transition point, corresponding to the formation of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. After two hours of heating, when the salt has the composition $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, the observational points shift to a third segment of the curve, where it is found that many molecules of nickel sulphate retain their last water of crystallisation even after prolonged heating for $5\frac{1}{2}$ hours. In the process of hydration of the anhydrous NiSO_4 at 32° the initial portion of the $N-t$ curve is almost straight, till 2.5 molecules of water of dehydration are absorbed per molecule of NiSO_4 . Then the points move to a second linear segment having smaller slope. In the next stage, after 4 molecules of water of hydration have been absorbed per molecule of the anhydrous salt, the points lie on a para-

bolic curve $N=at-bt^2$ as has been shown in in Fig. 2 of $N/t-t$ where a perfect straight line has been obtained (points marked with crosses). The unit of N/t as represented, is the number of molecule of H_2O gained per hour

FIG. 2.

per molecule of $NiSO_4$. The last molecule of water of hydration seems to be absorbed in perceptible quantity only after 25 hours. The velocity of dehydration curve shows distinct breaks at values of 'N' corresponding to 3, 5, and 6. This indicates the existence of hydrates having 4, 2, and 1 molecule of water of hydration. In order to see if the velocity of dehydration dies according to an exponential law, as is met with in radioactive transformation $\log dN/dt \rightarrow N$ graph is also drawn. It can be seen that the plottings can be grouped into 5 segments of which the first two are clear straight lines meeting at a sharp angle and the last three are approximately straight; but the position of the breaks on them also can be fixed up. There is no doubt that these breaks reveal the formation of hydrates having 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 molecules of water of hydration.